

EFFECT OF METACOGNITIVE LEARNING STRATEGY ON PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL PHYSICS STUDENTS' PROBLEM-SOLVING BEHAVIOUR IN SELECTED PHYSICS CONCEPTS IN BAUCHI, NIGERIA

Akpan, S. W.¹, Sa'adatu, A. M.², & Dauda, M. O.³

^{1,2,&3} Department of Science Education, Faculty of Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8310213>

Abstract

The study investigated the effect of metacognitive learning strategy on physics students' problem-solving behaviour in selected physics concepts. Three research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study design was a pretest and posttest randomized control group experiment. Two groups public senior secondary school students (n=22) participated in the study. During 4 weeks study, one group received the metacognitive strategy while the other group acted as control group with regular institutions. Data of the study were collected with two instruments, metacognitive awareness inventory (MAI) and physics problem-solving test behaviour (PPSTB). Findings of the study indicated that the strategy instruction was effective on physics problem-solving behaviour. The researcher recommended that the metacognitive learning strategy be informed into classroom instructions so that it could help students to learn their learning materials more efficiently and independently so as to become independent problems solvers.

Keywords: Metacognitive Learning Strategy, Metacognitive Awareness Level, Pretest, Posttest, Problem Solving Behaviour

Introduction

The main objective of educational institution is to facilitate the student's learning ability through setting up processes which must include goals setting, planning on how to achieve such goals, activating prior knowledge and relating them to new knowledge for a better comprehension of cognitive process, supervision, monitoring regulations and then reflecting on the entire learning processes of new information (Ball, 2016; Flavell, 1979).

The above highlighted learning processes are variables of metacognition which was first proposed by a developmental psychologist, John (1979) and defined as appraisal, monitoring and control of one cognitive process and metacognitive activities. Other scholars later on began relating metacognition to other constructs like, meta-learning, critical thinking, motivation and self-regulation especially in school-based activities (Salam et al., 2020). The knowledge aspects of metacognition include declarative, procedural and conditional while the self-regulatory aspect of it involves planning, monitoring and evaluation. It is these significant components of metacognition that ranks it as a key predictor of metacognitive learning awareness for physics students.

As these variables has impact positively on the development of student's metacognitive awareness, there is need to apply such learning processes to instruct students on physics problem-solving since there is a general speculation that

physics concepts and its principles are somewhat abstract and difficult to understand. But since physics can promote national development through its concepts and principles, there is a dire need to produce scientists that can move the country from where it was to the present state of 21st century as no country can develop or sustain any meaningful technology unless a good foundation is led (Enemali, 2016) through vigorous application of effective learning techniques which shall translate into good academic achievement for senior secondary school physics students.

Karaali (2015) asserts that many educators are currently teaching students using regular technique which usually result to low metacognitive awareness especially in abstract domain of physics, it is on this reason that the researchers sought to apply metacognitive learning strategy to determine its effects on senior secondary school problem-solving behaviour in selected physics concepts, motion and moment of force in Bauchi metropolis.

Statement of the Problem

There is a general speculation that the senior secondary school physics students (SSS) in the recent time are finishing the compulsory senior secondary school Certificate Examination (SSCE) in Nigeria with little or no mastery of the operational physics concepts knowledge and skills required in physics problem solving after leaving the school. The situation is unconnected with the 2017-2018 WASSC Chief Examiners report that Senior Secondary school physics knowledge is low especially in the area of mechanics which is often perceived difficult by students who seem reluctant to attempt to solve problems from this area. It is on this background that the researcher saw the need for Senior Secondary school physics students to become effective problems-solvers through the use of metacognitive learning strategy in physics as its importance necessitate the great developments across all fields of developments following its principles and concepts relevant in science and technology (Velloo, Nov, & Khalid, 2013).

Based on the above reasons, the best way to adapt to science and technology innovations is the need to facilitate students learning abilities in science Education, but unfortunately, our students display negative behaviours in classroom toward science subjects especially in physics which they speculate that it is full of abstract problem-solving nature that continues to influence fewer students to study physics related courses in higher institutions as oppose to other branches of science such as biology and chemistry (Guido, 2018). The fact that students' negative behaviour culminates into low metacognitive awareness competent. The researcher therefore sought to infuse metacognitive strategies into classroom instructions to determine its effect on student's awareness levels since the process involves planning, providing continuous feedback based on monitoring of the problem-solving process to enhance student's problem-solving competency.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determined effect of metacognitive learning strategy on public senior secondary school student's problem-solving behaviour in selected physics concepts (motion, moment of force). The specific objective of the study is to:

1. Determine the metacognitive awareness level of the public senior secondary school physics students before intervention
2. Find out effect of metacognitive learning strategy (MLS) on public senior secondary school physics students problem-solving behaviour after intervention

Research Questions

1. What is the metacognitive awareness level (MAL) of senior secondary school physics students before intervention?
2. What is the effect of metacognitive learning strategies (MLS) on public secondary school physics student's problem-solving behaviour after intervention?

Research Hypotheses

The hypothesis of the study was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H_{01} There is no significant difference between the physics problem-solving behaviour of the senior secondary school physics students taught physics using metacognitive learning strategy (MAS) and those taught using lecture method (LM).

Literature Review

The theoretical framework of this research study is based on the theory of metacognition by John Flavell (1970). Metacognitive theory is an explanation of knowledge interested in how human beings can actively monitor and regulate their own thoughts processes. Metacognition is defined by a developmental psychologist John H. Flavell (1970) as ability to control one's cognition, metacognition is explained as capacity to reflect on which cognitive skills we use to succeed in a given task. The father of this theory, John Flavell, reviewed metacognition as learners knowledge of their cognitions and defined it as knowledge and cognition about cognitive phenomena (Flavell, 1979). In recent time partnership of educational psychologist have identified self-regulation as part of metacognition used as one of the career skills necessary to prepare students for post-secondary education and workplace. The study focuses on the theory of metacognition because it identified and classified cognitive knowledge into declarative, procedural and strategic behaviour and cognitive skills into planning, monitoring and evaluation for better learning and awareness.

An article entitled "metacognitive skills and problem-solving" was published by Guner & Erbay (2021) to investigate the metacognitive strategy that middle school students used in the process of solving problem individually. The study comprised 37 participants in the eighth grade. The questionnaire was one non-routine word problem and their written answer were collected after solving the problems. The participants were asked to fill out a self-monitoring questionnaire that asked them to reflect retrospectively on the metacognitive strategies used for the problem solutions. The semi-structured interview followed to find out correctly students' responses, 3 out of 6 students correctly answered the questions. The results showed that metacognitive skills have a significant effect on student's problem-solving success. Showing that students with high metacognitive skills tend to solve the problem correctly using the appropriate strategies, mathematical notations and logical reasons unlike poor metacognitive skilled participants that have difficulties in understanding the problems.

Another article written by Djudin (2018) to examine the extent of effectiveness of integrating metacognitive strategies with transfer of learning of mathematics know edged in solving physics problems of sound wave using quasi-experimental method. The study had 39 students of class IV-A as experimental group and 58 students of class IV-B as control group in education faculty of Pontinanal university. The questionnaire of parallel pre-test and post-test of essay test of 5 items if sound intensely and Doppler effect were administered. The results revealed that the model was effective in

high category in increasing the student’s physics-problem-solving competencies ($t=2.594$, $P<0.05$). Also, the ability of transfer of learning in problem could be prompted as well.

Research Methodology

The research design employed for the study was pre-test and posttest randomized control group method. The population of the study was 9062 public senior secondary school students (SSSII) in Bauchi metropolis Nigeria. The sample and sampling technique employed was simple random sampling technique. The instruments for data collection were metacognitive awareness inventory (MAI) as first instruments having 19 items (graded on 5-point liker scale with the following options. 1=I never do it, 2= I do this not frequently, 3= I do this this inconsistently, 4=I do this frequently and 5= I do this always. The instrument was adopted from Schraw and Denison (1994) with validating index of 0.76 while the second instrument, physics problem-solving test behaviour (PPSTB) is self-developed by the researcher from SSSII physics students’ syllabus with 10 items. Having validity index 0.81 validation of the instruments were face validity and content validity undertaken dichotomously by two experts, 1 from measurement and Evaluation department of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University (ATBU) and one physics learning practitioner from Bauchi state ministry of education. The reliability of the instrument passed through Cronbach Alpha method for result consistency. The data were collected through giving metacognitive awareness competent test first to students before intervention in order to ascertain their metacognitive competent levels so that researcher could have accurate feedback to develop their metacognitive skills for physics problem-solving.

A four-week intervention followed in the selected topics of motion and moment of force for the two groups. The experimental group was instructed on metacognitive learning strategy while the control group continue to receive regular instructions. The data analysis for the study was done for both instrument through descriptive and inferential statistics of mean (\bar{X}) and standard deviation (D) and independent sample t-test. The null hypotheses were tested at $P<0.05$ level of significance while the discussion rules concludes that id validity is bigger than 0.80 it will be listed as very valid instrument.

Result and Discussions

Research Question One: What is the metacognitive awareness level (MAL) of senior secondary school physics students before intervention?

The descriptive statistics on research question one is as follows;

Table 1: Mean difference of experiment and control group before intervention

Variables	N	Mean (\bar{X})	Standard Deviation (SD)	Mean difference
Experiment	11	2.00	6.05	0.74
Control	11	1.36	6.30	

The result in table 1 showed that the students had a mean Metacognitive Awareness Level values as 2.00 and 1.36 respectively indicating a mean difference of 0.74 before intervention.

Research Question Two: What is the effect of metacognitive learning strategies (MLS) on public secondary school physics student’s problem-solving behaviour after intervention?

The descriptive statistics on research question one is as follows;

Table 2: Descriptive statistics on the mean difference of the experimental and control group after intervention are presented below.

Variables	N	Mean (\bar{X})	Standard Deviation (SD)	Mean difference
Experiment	11	59.82	2.86	14.01
Control	11	45.72	5.23	

The results in table 2 showed that the students in regular instruction method and metacognitive strategy (MLS) and their calculated mean score were 45.72 and 59.82 respectively showing a mean difference of 14.01.

Hypothesis:

H_{01} There is no significant difference between the physics problem-solving behaviour of the senior secondary school physics students taught physics using metacognitive learning strategy (MAS) and those taught using lecture method (LM).

Table 3: The t-test of the experimental and control group on metacognitive awareness level after intervention

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	t_{cal}	P	Decision
Experiment	11	4.19	.0619	20	2.88	0.05	Rejected
Control	11	3.38	.696				

Table 3 Shows a relative increase in the metacognitive awareness level of the group with a mean score (\bar{X}) of 3.38 and 4.19 and standard deviation of .0696 and .0619 after intervention respectively. The independent sample t-test was significant which makes the H_{01} to be rejected.

Discussion of the Findings

Metacognitive awareness level (MAL) of the senior secondary school physics students before intervention

The finding of the study revealed that Senior Secondary school (SSS) physics student’s metacognitive awareness was low before intervention using metacognitive learning strategy which consequently implies lack of metacognitive awareness skills to be able to select the expected metacognitive learning strategy to attempt solving the problem. This agrees with work of Ajmason and Singh (2016) which revealed that, after an intervention was applied on the Senior Secondary school physics students using the metacognitive awareness strategies, the student’s awareness was developed and improved, and that the senior secondary school students displayed a better behaviour towards awareness of their cognitions.

Effect of metacognitive leaving strategy (MLS) on senior secondary school physics student behaviour

The finding shows a relative increased in academic scores of students taught using metacognitive learning strategy, thus having effect on senior secondary school physics student problem-solving behaviour. This agrees with the work of Chan (2018) who also asserted that learners who utilized metacognitive regulation strategies such as planning, monitoring and evaluating have positively improved their behaviour towards problem-solving or any cognitive task.

Metacognitive awareness level of senior secondary school physics students after intervention

The finding indicates that the experimental group metacognitive awareness level is relatively better than the control group metacognitive awareness level after intervention. This agrees with the researchers Swee, Toh and Tai (2017) who asserted that students who were subjected in a class that require them to find answers to the given problems with the aid of metacognitive strategies demonstrated an improved behaviour towards problem-solving compared to a class where in the lecture methods were used in teaching high level of metacognitive awareness after intervention.

Conclusion

The results show that metacognitive strategies influenced problem-solving outcome positively, and students who were able to use metacognitive strategies gave correct answer to the problems. Also they were able to recognize problems requirements and objectives used for various solutions strategies and check the correctness of the solutions, but students who had low metacognitive awareness could not solve the problem successfully and they had difficulties in understanding the problem, finding solution strategies, and recognizing their errors. This implies lack of awareness of what and why they did while solving problem.

Recommendations

The study recommends that:

1. The senior secondary school II, physics students should be instructed using metacognitive strategy to enhance their low metacognitive level
2. Teachers should be encouraged to develop their relevant pedagogy through learning, monitoring and evaluation of their cognitive processes
3. Teachers should instruct their students to learn to monitor and evaluate their cognitive process.

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